

Cybersecurity for Safety: Risk Assessment of Autonomous Cyber-Physical Systems

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Abstract—Recent developments in Artificial Intelligence and Industry 4.0 have led to a new generation of autonomous Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs), including self-driving cars, unmanned aerial vehicles, and multi-robot systems, possibly operating in critical environments. With the increase in systems complexity, the distinction between safety and security becomes blurred, with cyber-attacks affecting both security and safety attributes of CPSs. Failures can potentially lead to severe consequences and hazards, such as environmental pollution and hazards to human operators. In light of the above, in this paper, we propose a novel risk assessment methodology tailored to safety- and security-critical CPSs. The methodology begins with identifying a specific threat scenario, enabling the analysis of risks caused by cyber-attacks. These risks are then evaluated in terms of safety and privacy using the EVITA approach. The methodology's effectiveness is demonstrated through a case study of an autonomous wheelchair within the REXASI-PRO European project.

Index Terms—Cyber-Physical Systems, Risk assessment, Autonomous Systems, Safety and Security integration, Artificial Intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) research and Industry 4.0 has led to the creation and spread of autonomous Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) operating in safety-critical environments. CPSs can be defined as computer systems that integrate sensing, control, and computation elements in order to execute a physical process [1]. In more specific terms, autonomous CPSs represent a class of devices, including self-driving cars, unmanned aerial vehicles, and certain kinds of robots, which consist of physical systems controlled by software that are envisioned to have no human operator [2]. However, this development process is not always accomplished with an appropriate security culture. In fact, during the early stages of CPS development, system designers typically paid more attention to safety issues [3] because safety and security have traditionally been regarded as distinct issues addressed by separate communities [4]. However, with the increasing complexity and integration among systems, the distinction between safety and security is beginning to wane [5]. At the same time, many CPSs have evolved to be not only

safety-critical but also security-critical due to their extensive integration of physical objects and computer networks [6]. Consequently, safety and security have become two principal aspects of CPSs, making it necessary to assess all associated risks to ensure both. Nevertheless, traditional risk assessment techniques analyze safety and security threats separately [7], which may be insufficient to address the interconnected nature of the risks in modern CPSs. In fact, modern CPSs encompass a heterogeneous and complex set of systems and devices, resulting in the absence of a standard that offers a step-by-step guide for risk assessment. Indeed, although several standards such as IEC 62443 [8] address aspects of industrial automation and control systems safety, they do not yet provide comprehensive guidance for CPS risk assessment. To fill this gap, the research community has explored various approaches to address CPSs safety and security challenges, such as STRIDE [9], OCTAVE [10], and MAGERIT [11]. Recent studies, including those by Lyu et al. [6] and Zografopoulos et al. [12], have evaluated existing methodologies and proposed hybrid frameworks combining qualitative and quantitative models. Amro et al. [13] proposed an approach utilizing FMECA [14] enhanced with the MITRE ATT&CK framework [15]. However, despite this could be a valid approach, they did not introduce an operational methodology for CPS risk assessment addressing both safety and security.

In light of the above, in this paper, we propose a novel risk assessment methodology for autonomous CPSs integrating both safety and security aspects. The developed methodology begins with an initial definition of the system components and the scenario under evaluation, followed by the identification and evaluation of risks using the E-safety Vehicle Intrusion Protected Applications (EVITA) approach [16]. It continues with the modeling of attacks using attack trees and concludes with the identification of countermeasures. The methodology is then validated with a case study of an Autonomous Wheelchair (AW) within the REXASI-PRO¹ European project,

¹ <https://rexasi-pro.spindoxlabs.com/>

which addresses indoor and outdoor use cases to demonstrate trustworthy social navigation of AWs together with flying drones in real-world environments [17].

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the proposed methodology; Section III focuses on the analysis of the case study; while Section IV concludes the paper.

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The prevailing security risk assessment methodologies, primarily confined IT security and compliance risk domains [18], often fail to address the full spectrum of potential risks in safety-critical environments. The proposed methodology proposes an approach for assessing cyber risk in such domains, with a particular focus on the analysis of the impact of threats from safety and privacy perspectives. The main phases of the methodology are presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Waterfall flowchart of the proposed methodology

A. Context definition

This step is inspired by the framework described in the ISO 31000 standard [19]. It involves defining the context, which entails describing the system to be analyzed and its surrounding environment. This phase requires delineating all the devices that constitute the system, the interconnections between them (wired, wireless, or otherwise) and the type of communication protocol employed, with particular attention to the elements of the system that comprise the attack surface. This phase includes two distinct analyses: a preliminary, high-level examination of the system's constituent devices, and a subsequent, in-depth investigation of each identified device. The former serves to identify the system's components, while the latter focuses on the individual elements of each device. To illustrate, a multi-robot industrial system would be analyzed in two stages. The initial analysis would identify the various robots and their communication. The subsequent analysis would then examine the components within the individual robots (sensors, actuators, cameras, etc.).

In the context definition phase, one or more scenarios can be defined to allow for a more detailed analysis. For instance, the analyst can consider the situation of a self-driving vehicle that must safely detect traffic lights and pedestrian crossings.

B. Attack goals identification

Once the system components and the attack surface have been defined, the second phase of our methodology involves examining the specific goals that a cyber attacker might aim to achieve, particularly those that impact the safety or privacy of the user interacting with the system or third parties in its proximity. The objectives of the attacker may include gaining unauthorized access to sensitive user data, manipulating or disrupting critical system functionality, exploiting vulnerabilities to compromise the integrity or availability of the system, and endangering the safety (or even the life) of users. Understanding the attacker's motivations allows for a more straightforward assessment of potential risks and the adaptation of defensive strategies in a manner that is commensurate with the identified severity. This proactive approach is crucial for the analysis, as it prioritizes the identification of attack goals (which remain constant) over attack vectors (which are continually evolving).

C. Vulnerability identification

In this phase, the vulnerabilities of the various devices and system components are identified. The process involves two main stages of analysis: an initial analysis, which is conducted using open source tools such as the NIST National Vulnerability Database (NVD) [20] or MITRE Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) [21] lists of known vulnerabilities, and a second, more in-depth analysis, which is conducted directly on the system using vulnerability assessment tools like OpenVAS². These steps ensure a robust assessment of the system's security posture, combining the breadth of public vulnerability databases with the depth of system-specific analysis.

D. Attack modeling

Building on the vulnerabilities identified in the previous step, we proceed to identify the attack vectors and the types of attack that a malicious agent may employ to achieve the objectives outlined in Section II-B. After delineating a comprehensive picture of the situation - including scenario, target, type, and attack vector - we delineate the path malicious actors might take to reach their objective, known as the attack path. This is illustrated using the attack tree model proposed by Bruce Schneier in [22]. In this model, rectangular blocks represent the various actions to be performed in order to reach the goal described in the root node. Links between the nodes represent a logical OR, while the AND is specified through a labeled arc. It should be noted that some nodes can be detailed with parameters. In the proposed methodology, certain nodes will be characterized by a tuple of parameters which will be described in detail in the next section.

E. Risk evaluation

The risk evaluation phase entails the assignment of a risk value to the threats identified through the use of attack trees. The risk is evaluated using EVITA and the approach proposed

² <https://www.openvas.org/>

by Sabaliauskaite et al. in [23]. EVITA is a suitable approach for evaluating concepts, but it requires excessive detail for classification and a significant amount of effort [24]. Consequently, based on [23], instead of evaluating threats in terms of elapsed time, expertise, knowledge of the system, window of opportunity, and equipment (as provided by EVITA), only the knowledge of the system (K) and the equipment (E) required to carry out the attack are used as evaluation metrics. Subsequently, a third evaluation metric, the potential P, which represents the probability that an attack will be successful, is determined by combining the values of the two preceding metrics. These three metrics are described in detail in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1
DESCRIPTION OF PARAMETERS K AND E

Parameter	Level	Description
Knowledge of the system (K)	0	No system knowledge
	1	Basic knowledge
	2	Complete and detailed knowledge
Equipment (E)	0	No specific equipment
	1	Standard equipment, easily obtainable
	2	Specialized equipment, not easily obtainable

TABLE 2
DESCRIPTION OF POTENTIAL (P) PARAMETER

Parameter	Level	(K, E)
Potential (P)	1 (Very Low)	(2,2)
	2 (Low)	(2,1), (1,2)
	3 (Medium)	(1,1), (2,0), (0,2)
	4 (High)	(0,1), (1,0)
	5 (Very High)	(0,0)

At this point, we proceed to classify the threats according to their degree of severity, in terms of privacy and safety. We utilize the EVITA approach, which classifies threats from a severity class of S0 (no impact) to a class of S4 (catastrophic impact), as illustrated in Table 3. Having defined these values, we can assign a level of risk R (ranging from 0, representing the lowest risk, to 6, representing the highest risk) to each threat using the risk matrix (Table 4) proposed by EVITA. Note that the S0 class is not considered in this risk assignment.

TABLE 3
SEVERITY CLASSIFICATION

Class	Safety	Privacy
S0	No injuries	No data access
S1	Light/moderate injuries	Anonymous data only (no specific user or system)
S2	Severe injuries (survival probable) Moderate injuries for multiple units	System specific data Anonymous data for multiple devices/components
S3	Life threatening or fatal injuries Severe injuries for multiple users or third parties	User identity compromised
S4	Fatal for multiple users or third parties	Sensitive data of user and system compromised

F. Countermeasures identification

This final point outlines measures to minimize threats identified in the preceding risk analysis. Countermeasures can

TABLE 4
LEVEL OF RISK DEFINITION

Level of risk (R)	Potential					
	P=1	P=2	P=3	P=4	P=5	
Severity	S1	0	0	1	2	3
	S2	0	1	2	3	4
	S3	1	2	3	4	5
	S4	2	3	4	5	6

be divided into two main categories: run-time and design-time. Run-time measures may include tools such as Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) and Intrusion Prevention Systems (IPSs), which continuously monitor the system to detect and respond to threats in real-time analyzing network traffic and system logs. IPSs not only detect but actively block threats. Additionally, Intrusion Response Systems (IRs) provide a structured approach to managing security incidents as they occur, enabling rapid assessment, containment, and mitigation. These systems are crucial for an active system protection and can help generate an Incident Response (IR) plan, which provides detailed guidelines and procedures to address and resolve security breaches, reducing the overall impact of incidents. One possible approach is the IR proposed by the SANS Institute [25], which consists of six basic points: *Preparation, Identification, Containment, Eradication, Recovery and Lessons Learned*. In contrast, design-time measures involve strategies and practices implemented during the system design phase to prevent vulnerabilities from the outset. This encompasses the adoption of security-by-design principles, such as minimizing privileges, utilizing robust security protocols and conducting code reviews and penetration tests. The objective of design-time measures is to construct an inherently secure system, thereby reducing the attack surface and mitigating risks before the system goes into production.

III. CASE STUDY: AUTONOMOUS WHEELCHAIR

The case study concerns an AW as part of the European REXASI-PRO project. The analysis was conducted in a controlled laboratory setting, with all penetration tests performed within the private network.

1) *Context definition*: According to the methodology described in Section II, the initial step is to define the context. This includes defining system characteristics, the operating environment, and, in this case, focusing the analysis on a precise scenario. The scenario under evaluation consists of a user sitting on AW who wants to cross the road, in the presence of other pedestrians and vehicles. The system in the case study comprises two devices: an AW and a drone. The system is isolated, with communications occurring only between the AW and the drone, and within the AW. The AW-to-AW communications are wired, while the AW-to-drone and drone-to-AW communications are wireless. The communication between the AW and the drone is based on ROS2 (Robot Operating System 2) [26], which employs the RTPS (Real-Time Publish-Subscribe) protocol. AW-to-AW communication

refers to the interaction between the various components of the wheelchair, which is primarily based on ROS2. In contrast to the drone, which is considered a single entity, the wheelchair comprises six main components:

- On-board PC (with Linux Ubuntu 20.04 LTS operating system)
- Human Machine Interface (HMI) (generic tablet with Android 11.0 operating system)
- Camera (Intel RealSense)
- LiDAR sensors (SICK TIM 2D model)
- Microelectronic board (STM32 Nucleo)
- Incremental encoder (GEL248V)

As previously stated, all components are wired. However, they are wired at different levels. The on-board PC, HMI tablet, camera, and microelectronic board have wiring at the network level. In contrast, the sensors and encoder are connected solely through wiring at the physical level. The sensors have a micro-USB port that has service and parameterization interface functions. The drone, assumed to be a DJI Spark model, communicates wirelessly with the AW. Details of the various connections are described below:

- PC, Tablet, camera, and microelectronics board are connected via Ethernet
- Microelectronics board and LiDAR sensor are connected via USB
- Microelectronics board and encoder have a custom data bus
- Drone and AW are linked via a WiFi 802.11ax

All communication is routed through the on-board PC, which serves as the central processing unit of the system. The PC receives raw data from the various AW components and the drone, processes it to assess the surroundings, evaluates risks, and makes decisions. Based on the analyzed situations and the decisions made, the PC then sends commands and instructions to the various AW components and the drone. Therefore, no device other than the PC is able to make autonomous decisions. The only decision not taken autonomously by the PC is the destination, which is transmitted from the user to the PC via the HMI. The system does not include remote control systems, making it completely autonomous. The on-board PC is the sole responsible entity for controlling the various components and the drone.

TABLE 5
IP ADDRESSES OF NETWORK 192.168.1.0/24

Device	IP Address
Onboard PC	192.168.1.2
Tablet (HMI)	192.168.1.3
Microelectronics board	192.168.1.10
Drone	192.168.1.20

2) *Attacker goals identification*: Having completed a comprehensive description of the system’s components, our attention was then directed towards identifying potential goals of attack within the scenario under consideration. In this context, two main macro-objectives were identified:

- *User physical damaging*: this objective implies a direct attack on the control system of the wheelchair, with the intention of compromising its integrity or manipulating its operation to cause injury to its user.
- *Theft of sensitive data*: this goal concerns the unauthorized access to sensitive data stored in the AW’s on-board PC or transmitted over the network. It is possible that attackers may seek to obtain the user’s personal information, including identification data and medical information, which could be used for malicious purposes such as identity theft, blackmail, or extortion.

3) *Vulnerabilities identification*: In accordance with the procedures delineated in Section II-C, the identification of vulnerabilities is conducted through the usage of open-source tools for the purpose of searching for known vulnerabilities (such as the CVE lists of MITRE and NIST) and through the use of specific vulnerability assessment tools (such as OpenVAS), which allow a more comprehensive assessment of potential weaknesses in the system. Following a meticulous examination, several vulnerabilities were identified in the system under review. Table 6 presents the most relevant vulnerabilities in terms of their potential impact on security and the associated Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) score.

TABLE 6
MAIN SYSTEM CVEs

Device	Vulnerability	CVSS Score
Onboard PC	CVE-2020-1472	9.3
	CVE-2020-12284	10
	CVE-2022-0543	10
Tablet HMI	CVE-2020-8899	9.8
Camera	CVE-2023-29504	7.8
Drone	CVE-2022-46415	9.1

4) *Attack modeling*: At this point, two attack trees (Figures 2 and 3) are constructed, one for each of the goals described in Section III-2. The objective is to reconstruct the paths taken by adversaries to perform their attacks. These attacks lead to several threats which, in turn, allow adversaries to reach their final goal. The root node of each tree represents the attack goal, followed by nodes identifying the threats posed by the attacks, and subsequently, the nodes describing the attack paths. Latter nodes are characterized by a tuple of parameters (P, K, E) representing the potential, the knowledge of the system, and the equipment required to accomplish a specific attack step. It should be noted that the proposed attack trees are not intended to provide an exhaustive description of all possible attack paths and vectors. The purpose of these trees is solely to illustrate and validate the methodology employed in this specific case study. A comprehensive analysis of all potential attack vectors is impractical and not the primary objective of this work.

5) *Risk evaluation*: This phase consists of assigning a risk level to each threat based on the average of the parameter values associated with each step in the attack paths. In this way, we can assess the overall risk associated with each threat, by considering both its potential P and severity S on the

Fig. 2. Attack tree for user physical damaging goal

system. To calculate the risk level, the following steps have been followed:

- *Attack tree analysis*: for each attack tree, all the potential pathways an adversary could use to successfully achieve their goal have been examined.
- *Impact assessment*: the severity level S for each threat has been assessed by considering the final attack goal of the specific attack tree.
- *Average computation*: for each threat, the average of the P values associated with each attack path leading to that threat has been calculated.
- *Risk level assignment*: starting from S and P values calculated in previous steps and using the matrix outlined in Section II-E, the risk level for each threat has been assessed (Table 7).

TABLE 7
RISK LEVEL ASSIGNMENT

Attacker goal	Threat	Severity	Potential	Level of Risk
User physical damaging	Compromise decision-making process	4	3	4
	Prevent data processing of onboard PC	3	4	4
	Inject commands from AW to drone	4	4	5
	Inject video data from drone to AW	4	4	5
	Communication delay between AW and drone	3	4	4
	Communication interruption between AW and drone	4	4	5
Sensitive data theft	Data exfiltration from AW components	4	3	4
	Sniffing data from AW and drone communication	2	4	3

6) *Countermeasures*: In order to address the identified vulnerabilities and mitigate the associated risks, a number of countermeasures have been identified for potential adoption. Firstly, the potential countermeasures must be categorized into two distinct classes: design-time countermeasures and runtime countermeasures. With regard to design-time countermeasures, the first step is to encrypt all communications. ROS2-based systems transmit messages in plaintext by default, necessitating the enabling of SROS2 (*Secure ROS2*). SROS2 enables the implementation of authentication policies, access control, encryption, logging, and data tagging. Another potential solution to address design-time vulnerabilities is the implementation of authentication mechanisms, particularly device-based authentication, to ensure that only authorized devices are able to communicate with the AW. This can be achieved through the use of mutual TLS or similar protocols. Then, in order to mitigate the risk of exploiting known vulnerabilities, a countermeasure to be taken is to ensure that all system components are constantly updated with the most recent firmware and software versions. With regard to countermeasures at runtime, it is possible to adopt an Intrusion Detection and Prevention System (IDPS) that, by analyzing network traffic, can detect possible attacks in real time. This system is able to send alerts in the event that any anomalies are identified and to process an automatic response in order

Fig. 3. Attack tree for theft of sensitive data goal

to counteract the attack in real time.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have developed a novel risk assessment methodology for autonomous CPSs, emphasizing the importance of considering safety and security aspects simultaneously. The increasing complexity and integration between systems necessitate a holistic approach that acknowledges their interdependence. The proposed methodology enables the identification of specific threat scenarios, the analysis of the risks posed by cyber-attacks, and the evaluation of these risks in terms of safety and privacy. The practical application of the methodology on an autonomous wheelchair within the REXASI-PRO European project provides evidence of its effectiveness in real-world contexts. Future work will enhance the methodology by incorporating additional formalisms, such as Bayesian networks, to improve threat probability calculations and overall risk assessment and will provide practical guidance for effective implementation in other CPS environments.

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